

Developing co-diagnostic activities as part of unlearning: reporting on the Linear Park of Pedieos River

Charalampos Spanos, Georgios Artopoulos, Constantinos Kritiotis, Afroditi Magou

Abstract

The concept of Nature-based solutions (NBS) is a recent one that brings together solutions and approaches that are inspired and supported by nature, promising to simultaneously provide environmental, social and economic benefits towards more sustainable communities. The paper reflects on ongoing experiences of unlearning in the context of new research developed for an urban riverbed that lies next to a recently urbanized historical built environment in the Eastern Mediterranean island of Cyprus. The paper presents a roadmap of learning about the local participatory culture and the perspectives around public green spaces located in the Pedieos river, which has a great environmental and ecological importance for the urban environment, as part of a larger unlearning process. In this exploration, the research presented comes across official and unofficial barriers that local stakeholders are asked to unlearn through participation and collaboration among different agencies, including governmental and local authorities, NGOs, and local communities. The research is experimenting with diverse participatory methods in order to engage underrepresented social groups, elderly, youth and children, while raising awareness regarding the importance of preserving biodiversity and promoting human-nature relationship. These methods include phygital interaction with nature and field exploration, open discussions framed by data-driven insights and serious geo-games of scenario testing for decision-making. Acknowledging that the local community has knowledge to share, the research employs citizen science, aiming to encourage participants to share their knowledge.

Keywords

Living Labs, Knowledge Co-production, Participatory Methodology, Citizen Science, Strovolos

Acknowledgments

TRANS-lighthouses is a European-funded Horizon Project (grant agreement no. 101084628)

1. Introduction

1.1. *New Approaches to Implementing Nature-based Solutions*

Nature-based solutions (NBS) have been acknowledged as a significant approach to transitioning our heavily and increasingly expanding urbanized environment to more sustainable, climate-adapted, and inclusive futures. Numerous efforts are being made to learn from a global outpost to incorporate practical knowledge and contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the appropriate methods and tools of NBS implementation in diverse conditions and locales (World Bank, 2021). Going beyond singular approaches to studying the implementation of NBS from a disciplinary perspective, the presented research is part of a broader effort to construct new, hybrid, and integrated, understandings of the key components that make up the complexity of developing social and ecological just NBS. In this effort, the importance of socio-political considerations is emphasized as an integral part of the public agenda for nature-based solutions advocating for systemic change.

By prioritizing citizens' engagement in decision-making participatory processes and the inclusion of marginalized knowledge, the project¹ to which the presented research contributes investigates tools and methodologies for citizen science in co-diagnostic phases, to form common understandings, as the first step for collaborative governance (Fig.2). Ultimately, the aim of this activity is to contribute to the establishment of a living knowledge lab to encompass different knowledge, experiences, and roles, within a multi-stakeholder dialogue.

A living knowledge lab will be developed in the area of the Pedieos River Linear Park in Strovolos, Cyprus to test innovative approaches to NBS implementation through participatory practices that engage diverse voices, including governmental agencies, local authorities, independent organizations active in Cyprus, community organizations, and community members. A great focus is given to the representation of marginalized and underrepresented voices, such as youth, the elderly, and migrants.

This paper presents the methodology we implemented during the co-diagnostic phase of the pilot², to document local knowledge and to communicate experts' opinions to the community for the challenges identified for the pilot's area. This approach provides a platform for learning and unlearning, ensuring the legitimization of community knowledge and expectations, as well as the adaptation of new beliefs, that leads to a process of unlearning (Nygren et al., 2017). The overall co-diagnostic phase contributes to the co-production of knowledge, through the integration of diverse tools and methods, creating a baseline for collaborative NBS implementation (Fig.1). What follows in this section regards the main contexts of the use case to be presented, namely the framework of governance and the territorial context of Strovolos.

¹ Horizon Europe TRANS-lighthouses project addresses the NBS challenges identified under the projects URNiNAT, UNaLab, PHUSICOS, and Nature4Cities. The lighthouses of the project, including pilot cases and assessment cases, create a body of knowledge on participatory practices towards the implementation of NBS and the formation of a just, inclusive, and innovative co-governance model.

² Pilot of Pedieos River Linear Park in Strovolos Municipality, Nicosia region, Cyprus

Figure 1: Conceptual Diagram of Co-diagnostic approach followed for the co-production of knowledge

1.2. Collaborative Governance

Collaborative governance is defined by Ansell & Gash (2008) as “a governing arrangement where one or more public agencies directly engage non-state stakeholders in a collective decision-making process that is formal, consensus-oriented, and deliberative and that aims to make or implement public policy or manage public programs or assets” (ibid., p. 544). They argue that the emergence of collaborative governance comes as an alternative to traditional regulatory and managerial methods, which have been proven to be ineffective, and may not always produce the desired outcomes. Co-governance offers a growth of knowledge and complexity, bringing diverse stakeholders together to collaborate over multi-aspect governance. Such a collaborative approach can better respond to the complexity of contemporary challenges that require interdisciplinarity and user-oriented development and policy-making (ibid.).

Furthermore, co-governance, by providing a platform for dialogue and negotiation, can contribute to enhanced legitimacy and trust among stakeholders, improved social acceptance and inclusion with marginalized and vulnerable voices being heard, and therefore committing them to the project and ensuring its longevity and resilience. Their involvement develops a sense of ownership, which can lead to better maintenance and care, while adjusting strategies based on ongoing feedback and changing conditions, thus dealing with unforeseen uncertainties and complexities (Frantzeskaki, 2019).

Figure 2: A model of collaborative governance (Ansell & Gash, 2008)

1.3. Strovolos Pilot

Strovolos Municipality was established in 1986 and it counts over 70,000 inhabitants in an area of 25 km², making it the second largest municipality in Cyprus after Limassol (Strovolos Municipality, 2024). Pedieos is an ephemeral river that flows from an elevation of 1400 m above sea level in the Troodos mountains. The river runs through four highly urbanized municipalities, including Strovolos, and has contributed to several flooding hazards in the cities. It currently, also, functions as a linear park for urban residents with several adjacent activities, a pedestrian, and a cycling path (Giannakis et al., 2016). The specific pilot was selected as an opportunity to rethink the reciprocal human-nature relationship in urban environments and the co-benefits of NBS for the improvement of the river's ecosystem through an innovative governance model. With the growing urbanization and the pressure applied to the river's ecosystem, the presented research calls for action toward collaborative efforts for resilient cohabitation between humans and nature.

1.4. Cyprus governance model

Cyprus has a highly centralized governance model (Fig.3), where the local governments - municipalities - operate under significant oversight from the central government, with the district's office coordinating the central government's activities and overseeing local councils' legal compliance. Although municipalities have some autonomy, their financial and administrative powers are limited, often requiring the central government's approval for major projects and budgetary decisions. Thus local governments are challenged with limited decision-making power, resource constraints, and a lack of a strategic vision for local development. Therefore, the engagement of the community in the decision-making process is generally limited, even though local authorities are primarily handling issues directly impacting residents' daily lives (Trutkowski et al., 2017).

Figure 3: Cyprus' governance model, illustrated by the authors, based on (Trutkowski et al., 2017)

2. State of the art

2.1. Participation and community knowledge for NBS

NBS has gained prominence as a sustainable approach to addressing urban challenges in the social, environmental, and economic dimensions. More interest is growing in the role of Urban Living Labs (ULLs) for the co-creation and co-implementation of NBS, creating multi-scalar stakeholder partnerships to collaborate on participatory processes (Mahmoud & Morello, 2021) and to radically rethink public spaces (Noll et al., 2020). Participation can be a decisive factor in the social acceptance and support of the local community to the NBS implementation while encouraging shared responsibility (Frantzeskaki, 2019; Nature4Cities, 2018). Especially the inclusion of underrepresented social groups, such as the elderly, youth, and minorities, can foster a sense of ownership, promoting long-term sustainability (Brennan et al., 2007; Lekies et al., 2009). The inclusion of youth can also encourage innovation, as fresh perspectives and ideas can bring creativity and effectiveness (Iwasaki, 2016). Local knowledge creates a better foundation for the planning and implementation of NBS. Residents, as users of the specific place, can provide valuable experiences on the value and the functionality of space, contributing to tailoring the planned NBS (Nature4Cities, 2018)

Numerous researches have been implemented on participatory processes, methodologies, and tools. More specifically, the European Commission has lately endorsed research on NBS and participatory processes, including recent European-funded Projects, such as URBiNAT, UNaLab, PHUSICOS, and Nature4Cities. UNaLab explains that stakeholder engagement is a process to engage people who “affect or are affected” by a decision. Importantly, they suggest that the level of engagement of each stakeholder may vary throughout the timeline of a project, based on their different interests, and thus it is essential to have all actors informed on all the processes and activities of the project (UNaLab, 2019). At the same time, PHUSICOS identifies critical challenges and success factors for Living Labs, including establishing a “clear, common, and accessible project terminology”, creating a strong “social inclusiveness and stakeholder representation”, professionally facilitating participation with early on and systematic design, as well as achieving an “iterative knowledge exchange” (PHUSICOS, 2018, pp. 27–35). Learning from

these projects, the research presented investigates methodologies for stakeholder engagement and participatory processes that promote inclusivity and encourage the involvement of underrepresented and vulnerable communities, to form Living Knowledge Labs (LKL) in pilot areas, toward implementing inclusive NBS and agile co-governance models.

2.2. Co-diagnostic operations as a process towards the co-production of knowledge

Co-diagnostic is a process of formalizing a common understanding, along with key stakeholders, relevant to the project, that would initiate the co-creation phase. To achieve this common understanding, stakeholder engagement is essential from the beginning.

This knowledge co-production is best illustrated in the way Caitana & Moniz (2024) implemented a methodology that entailed the engagement of stakeholders through one-to-one meetings, focusing on the involvement of the municipal government at first, and later the local association and institutions, to create synergies with other local projects. Afterward, they targeted local primary schools to collect the challenges and needs of the kids, and to conclude with a final public outreach event for the collection of data and interest in the project (Caitana & Moniz, 2024, p. 8; URBiNAT, 2019, p. 262). As the authors describe, this multi-scalar stakeholder network co-produced knowledge and activated a Living Lab that identified challenges and needs that were later considered during the co-creation phase.

Conducting co-diagnostic operations, inevitably, leads to the co-production of knowledge. Knowledge co-production for sustainable research is defined by Norström et al. (2020) as “iterative and collaborative processes involving diverse types of expertise, knowledge and actors to produce context-specific knowledge and pathways towards a sustainable future” (Norström et al., 2020, p. 183). Their work illustrates four principles necessary for knowledge co-production. Knowledge should be *contextualized*. Context could be place-based, and/or defined by specific issues, while also considering the affected actors and their needs. The process needs to be *pluralistic*, containing multidisciplinary academics and non-academics, to share knowledge and perspectives. They should collaboratively clarify ‘*defined and meaningful goals*’ which will orient the process. And finally, *interactivity* is a key element. The different participants should interact and collaborate in a structured and frequent manner (Norström et al., 2020). A formalized Living Lab creates a backbone of collaborative endeavors since the participants are already engaged and interested in a process that mandates synergistic activities.

The co-diagnostic process is one of the early stages of action for establishing a Living Lab. It requires collaboration, negotiation, and clear communication, that results in a definition of a common understanding. A structured co-diagnostic methodology can create a strong foundation for a Living Lab to engage in co-creation and co-implementation practices. Importantly, this process offers a platform for diverse stakeholders to share knowledge and contribute to a knowledge hub, that can fuel future processes, but also through negotiation, realize the behaviors and routines that need to be discarded, to “make way for new ones”, for a more sustainable society (Tsang & Zahra, 2008, p. 1437).

2.3. Learning to unlearn

Unlearning plays a significant role in co-producing knowledge that will contribute to transitioning to more sustainable futures. This adaptation process, which is iterative and interactive, and involves “adopting new beliefs by way of discarding previous beliefs” (Nygren et al., 2017, p. 474) is found in literature, especially organizational and managerial, as the unlearning process. Unlearning is only supported by learning (such as a co-diagnostic activity) that brings to the surface norms and routines, collectively considered not effective anymore, and therefore unveils the need to intentionally discard them (Tsang & Zahra, 2008).

Vetter (2020) talks about social unlearning, and how it can contribute to reshaping the dominant discourse. Specifically, he describes how a specific community of practice³ (CoP), in that case agri-food industry, can exchange and legitimize (practice-based) knowledge to reach a broader audience and initiate a transformation phase by making space for learning through unlearning. This process not only rethinks and reframes the dominant practice but also de-marginalizes the community’s knowledge toward more sustainable practices and regimes (Vetter, 2020).

In this context, the presented research focuses on the development and implementation of a participatory methodology for initiating the process that will lead to the establishment of a Living Knowledge Lab in Strovolos by means of co-diagnostic activities that would help the authors to engage local communities and mapped stakeholders in the co-production of local knowledge, the identification of unsustainable practices and beliefs, and the intentional collective adaptation of new ones (unlearning).

3. Methodology

These co-diagnostic activities aimed at legitimizing local community knowledge regarding the Pedieos River Linear Park, which was selected by the research for an NBS implementation. The methodology used was structured to encourage participants to exchange knowledge and negotiate toward a common understanding. Experts⁴ were involved in the activities to trigger discussions that would enable the authors to identify unsustainable practices, behaviors, and routines that the community needs to unlearn if they want to transition to more sustainable futures. These activities led to the organization of a workshop that served as the initial phase of the formalization of a Living Lab in Strovolos that can co-govern the implementation and maintenance of an NBS in the Linear Park with the participation of local authorities, NGOs, local community groups, and residents associations and individuals. The overarching goal of this effort is to accelerate the updating of the relevant policies, the adoption of new co-governance models, and behavioral change as well as to offer a good practice for multiplication in other areas.

The methodology presented below was implemented through the use of specific tools that were selected to facilitate collaboration and negotiation among the diverse stakeholders. At the same time, the structure of the sessions of said workshop ensured that community (living) knowledge was first documented formally, following specific templates of topics for discussion that would be introduced in the working groups. Later in the workshop, the experts’ input would trigger the negotiation of current practices and by doing so would identify bottlenecks.

³ “Communities of practice are groups of people who share a concern, a set of problems, or a passion about a topic, and who deepen their knowledge and expertise in this area by interacting on an ongoing basis”, (Wenger et al., 2004, p. 4)

⁴ Experts for the purpose of this workshop, refer to the representatives of NGOs that participated and presented their experience and scientific knowledge on the topics of the workshop.

*Figure 4: Co-diagnostic workshop methodology to trigger unlearning for NBS implementation
(illustrated by the authors)*

3.1. Communication strategy and participation

Prior to the workshop, the authors conducted one-to-one meetings with various NGO members for several months. It is also critical to mention that since the beginning of the activities, representatives of the technical support team of the local Municipality were engaged in the operations. In addition, the authors have been engaged in local outreach activities and visits to community associations for the promotion and dissemination of our activities. These in-person meetings with the community during outreach events were very beneficial, as the authors had the opportunity to present and discuss the objectives of the LL so that people would be aware of what to expect from the workshop. Not overlooking, of course, the online social media campaign that was empowered with the network of the involved NGOs, whose support during the activities and before, promoted a collaborative approach towards the implementation of the methodology.

As a result of this integrated communication strategy, the workshop consisted of 31 participants, including 7 members of the research team, 6 representatives of 4 different NGOs, 1 municipal officer, 4 elected members of the City Council, and 13 community members, consisting of members of the local residents' association, senior residents, middle-aged and youth. The participation of official municipal representatives was very positive for the community, as they had the opportunity to discuss and express their opinions, ensuring that the results of the workshop were communicated to the authorities and policymakers.

3.2. Introduction to the topic

To properly engage the target community of the project and create excitement for the process, the workshop's introduction needed to present the general concept of NBS and the resulting co-benefits of its implementation. The same importance was given to the goals and objectives of the overall research project, explaining specifically the significance of citizen participation and the role of the community in the decision-making process, co-creation, co-implementation, and co-monitoring. After the presentation, the participants had the opportunity to pose questions and get clarifications on both the process of the workshop and the project itself.

The kick-off activity was an exercise for the participants to divide into working groups while introducing themselves, even though many locals were already acquaintances. The topics of the three working groups, namely *biodiversity & environment*, *public space & activities*, and *mobility & accessibility*, allowed the participants to select a category based on their interests, knowledge, and experiences and announce it to the rest of the group. This activity was an icebreaker, as participants started talking to each other, and were more comfortable sharing their opinions in the working groups later.

To ensure at least age diversity in each working group, there was a pre-defined number of participants per age group for each topic. All participants happily joined this effort, verifying the importance of diverse voices in the decision-making process and collaborative approaches. Organically, each group had also at least one elected municipal councilor, while the municipal officer was happy to split their time among all three working groups.

In each working group, two members of the research team would participate as moderators of the discussion. Templates with topics for discussion were prepared (see Figure 4 and Appendix 1), and the moderators' role was to lead the discussion, keep the time frame, document the knowledge co-produced, identify any conflicts, or discrepancies that could fuel the reflection session, and initiate a discussion for unlearning. The workflow followed the principles of the World Café Method (Innovation Training, n.d.),

adjusted to the specificities of the workshop. In general, all working groups had round-table discussions, facilitated everyone's contribution, and encouraged diverse opinions.

Figure 5: Fill-in templates for each working group, with pre-defined topics for discussion (created by the authors)

3.3. Legitimizing Community Knowledge

To initiate the discussion, a *Storytelling method* was used which involved prescribed stories that were written drawing on the results of the prior territorial mapping exercise, as well as the behavioral and cultural context of the project. Narratives have always been used in participatory design to communicate and deliver concepts and information (Fassi et al., 2021). In this co-diagnostic exercise, narratives were used to stimulate discussions and create a canvas over which participants could express their points of view.

Each group of participants was given a set of stories relevant to their topic. The stories would have the form of testimonies and experiences described by fictional personas including diverse demographics (kids, elders, migrants) and different animals found in the Pedieos River's ecosystem. The following example demonstrates the structure of the stories:

“I am Kostas and I live with my wife and children in the Strovolos area, next to the linear park. This has its pros and cons. First, we have easy access to the pedestrian path, where we go for a walk with the children every Sunday afternoon. Also my wife uses it daily for jogging. On the other hand, passers-by often pass through our garden, at the point where it joins the pedestrian path, talking loudly and walking over the children's toys that remain in the garden.”

The concept of each story would bring to the table a conflict faced by the narrator, for example, someone living on the banks of the river, could be happy about having green space in proximity, but wouldn't like the people that make noise during the night. Therefore, the participants could either relate to the narrator and support the arguments in the story or be on the other side of the story as a park user, and counter-argue.

In practice, this method appeared very effective, as the participants would randomly pick a story, and therefore an element of surprise was in place. Then, each of them would have to read the story aloud

and make a comment, with the rest of the group having the opportunity to respond and discuss. This way, participants would bring to the table their own experiences as arguments for their points, and therefore, the researcher in each team could document the relevant living knowledge of the community. In some cases, the stories would trigger a very passionate and argumentative discussion that could take place the whole time, and in other cases, the stories would quickly find common ground among the participants.

To facilitate the discussion, the research team prepared a board with data, including maps of the area, photos, and other data related to each topic, such as transport/traffic network, climate data, biodiversity data, etc. Another useful tool for this session was the 360° video of the linear park, captured by the research team for this workshop. This video would allow the participants to place-base their stories/narratives/experiences as presented to the rest of the group. Especially for older participants who would describe locations based on memory and residents or shops, having this video for the walkthrough helped all members of the group to be more deeply involved in the conservation.

Narratives documented during this session “contribute to creating links with the space and to grow a sense of belonging”, enabling citizen science and participation in placemaking (Costa et al., 2024). The deep experience of residents provides valuable input for the research team to better understand the context and the community involved in the projects including their diverse backgrounds and opinions, that enrich the co-produced knowledge.

3.4. Experts' Contribution

The next session of the working groups would allow the experts, who had already participated in the previous discussion, to present their knowledge, based on their experiences and practice. A different expert was engaged in each working group, based on their expertise and experience.

For the *biodiversity & environment* working group, a researcher introduced environmental issues and ecosystem challenges, related to the Pedieos River. This information was shared informally, and in a discursive manner, allowing the participants to clarify and pose questions continuously. The invited researcher, along with two participants with a research background in environmental studies, shared facts about the ecosystem with the rest of the group and opted toward forming a communal understanding of the challenges of biodiversity, especially with the critical issue of excessive stray cat population and its impact on other species in the park.

The *public space & activities* working group hosted two experts from NGOs. The experts presented the risks around the capacity of a highly dense and paved urban environment to handle flooding events, as flooding has been a great challenge for Strovolos historically, and today, posing a consideration for safety along with other insights for the area. Their contribution to the discussion, mainly focused on broadening the views of the participants, regarding the possible functionalities of public space, and the opportunities to rethink the activities associated with public life, including matters of environment, climate change, and circular economy.

In the third working group, *mobility & accessibility*, two NGOs participated with a couple of representatives each. With their expertise in issues of sustainable mobility and rethinking streetscape, moving away from car-centric cities, AI, tactical urbanism, and smartphone applications focused on the social inclusion of people with disabilities (PwD), the experts discussed how regulations can be applied in public spaces in the specific territory. The opportunity for the community to pose questions and be engaged with experienced individuals was very important, to understand that a collaboration of diverse stakeholders is a necessity for informed and inclusive decision-making.

3.5. Conclusion - Triggering Unlearning

The last session was built around a custom-built version of the Visual Story tool, which helps the participants envision the future after the implementation of the project in a collaborative approach (De Vicente Lopez & Matti, 2016, pp. 118–121). Each working group worked on the Visual Story tool, to prioritize challenges, define the main bottlenecks that the solution will have to tackle, and plan a strategy, including the key stakeholders that need to be involved. In this process, participants were asked to consider routines and practices that are not sustainable and the actions that should take place to achieve their goals.

The Visual Story tool consisted of a News Title in the future, encouraging the participants to think of how their efforts would be communicated publicly. By realizing that, they had to understand why they decided to go in this direction, by clearly defining the material and immaterial challenges of today, including infrastructure, policy, behaviors, and routines. The next step would be to collaborate on the steps they had to follow, and what methods would need to be employed to make their vision a reality. Also, they needed to map the relevant stakeholders, from public authorities to the private sector, and the community. Finally, the group had to describe where this process would lead and how the changes would take place in their daily lives, with a proposal of the next steps they could take upon achieving their goal.

The tool was a great exercise for the working groups to understand the complexity of planning a strategy for a specific challenge, and the interconnectedness and collaboration required among stakeholders for a holistic strategy. It also allowed creative thinking and the diversity of the participants could contribute in different ways to the completion of this exercise, and derive specific conclusions based on the discussions before.

The wrap-up session took place at the end of the workshop and consisted of the presentation of each working group's Visual Story tool to the rest of the participants, by the moderators of each team. After each presentation there was time for suggestions and questions to be posed, allowing for more contribution to the final product. Hence, each workshop participant was informed of the conclusions and reflections of the different working groups.

4. Results

The results of the workshop were collected by means of two methods. For the two first sessions, the "Legitimization of Community Knowledge" and the "Discuss with the Experts", one of the moderators acted as a reporter. Their job was to moderate the discussion keeping in mind the three dimensions of importance that should be introduced, namely the participatory culture, the routines and behaviors of the community, and the experiences of the participants.

For the last reflective session, the participants had to complete an exercise using the Visual Story Tool. By first selecting a specific topic they were interested in addressing, they would form a strategy of actions that need to be taken, including identifying the main challenges, the stakeholders involved, the steps that need to be taken, and envisioning the future accomplishment they would achieve upon taking action. Using this tool, the research aimed to introduce the complexity of a collaborative approach towards decision-making, as well as triggering topics for unlearning within the community and current practices. At the end of the activity, everyone received a short questionnaire to be filled with questions about the content, the organization, and their involvement in the workshop.

Below, the results produced are presented, organized per working group and method of collecting data. All results are elaborated in Appendixes 1 and 2, in the form of tables.

4.1. Biodiversity & Environment

Community Living Knowledge and Discussion with Experts: the discussion held by the working group of Biodiversity & Environment underlined major points and identified some realities related to participatory culture in Cyprus, community routines, behaviors, and experiences that participants face every day in their interactions with the park.

Over the years, human activities, such as the introduction of invasive species and water management through damming and diversion, have been very impactful on the ecosystem and resulted in pollution and flooding events. Indeed, it was rightly pointed out during discussions that there is an urgent need for extensive environmental education that would increase awareness about local species and ecosystems, and the challenges associated with them. Experiences in the park indicate that plastic containers for cat food are sources of pollution as well, and food put out attracts possibly dangerous wildlife like foxes. While maintaining stray cats leads to indirect environmental impacts, sterilization drives become unavoidable to reverse the situation. Besides, contaminated water also creates health hazards for the ecosystem and visitors alike in the park. Amid all these negatives, this act of cat maintenance indirectly sustains several other species, like birds, which drink water kept for the cats.

Figure 6: Visual Story of Biodiversity & Environment Working Group

The Visual Story exercise of this group involved a strategy to reduce the population of stray cats in the Pedieos River Linear Park by 75% through constant sterilization. This acknowledges the ecological impact of the growth of cats as an invasive species. Such initiative defines what responsible animal care is, and has to overcome political and bureaucratic barriers.

Central measures implemented included a massive communications campaign, drawing upon best practices in other countries, awareness-raising, and securing the full participation of all the actors involved. The horizon for these measures is 2030; that is, correct and transparent communication, carrying out an integral strategy, respecting shared public spaces, and applying due sanctions. This, therefore, emphasizes the issue of collaborative and continued efforts in environmental management.

4.2. *Public Space & Activities*

Community Living Knowledge and Discussion with Experts: some of the main challenges and opportunities concerning Pedieos River Linear Park were defined here, e.g., the decision-making process is also multi-agency-led at the government, municipality, and police levels since a major issue concerns safety in the park. It was reported that, for the most part, this process is bureaucratic, while effective participatory practices are missing. To overcome this challenge, collaborative initiatives and volunteerism must be encouraged, engaging and promoting a culture of accountability from a variety of stakeholders. This is also encumbered by jurisdictional limitations and a lack of accountability of the government and municipality.

Routines and behaviors noted by the group concerned the cultural gap in appreciating urban nature. The linear park is crucial for jogging, cycling, and other physical activities. Biophilia and closeness to nature can contribute much to the improvement of mental health especially in our post-COVID, digital world (Sue, 2017). Hence, there is an absolute need to promote nature-based solutions and environmentally enhanced awareness. Through discussion, it became evident that a participatory tool for citizens is necessary, for them to raise their concerns and report back on the issues continuously.

Experiences shared by the community underline that it is a major free public green space within an urbanized area, serving primarily exercise and leisure purposes for migrants and Cypriots. Access problems, because of overgrown vegetation and flooding, and light problems make visitors feel unsafe during night visits. The poor maintenance has rendered a public space inaccessible and highly unsafe for people with disabilities. Nonetheless, the park offers great potential for sustainable energy and circular economy practices through activities related to youth and schools. Playground facilities with kiosks and restroom facilities can further the development value of the park.

Figure 7: Visual Story of Public Space & Activities Working group

“A Safe Linear Park for All, All Day Long” aims at upgrading the Pedieos River Linear Park through collaboration between the community, government, and NGOs. Proposals critical to this initiative include the maintenance of the riverbank, cleanliness, and collaborative spirit. This is essential to tackle Issues such as enhancing safety by reducing fears of attacks, facilities such as restrooms and clean water, and adequate lighting and maintenance.

By 2025, emergency spots will be available every few kilometers, with consistent lighting and a leash law for dogs, along with a 24/7 safety team including a hotline that would be provided. Other priorities include defibrillator installations, rigorous park maintenance, and the formation of a regular patrol team that will ensure its safety and upkeep. The initiative looks into a future time when the park is well-maintained, accessible, and safe.

4.3. Mobility & Accessibility

Community Living Knowledge and Discussion with Experts: Decision-making at all levels should therefore be truly collaborative between government agencies, scientists, researchers, and social groups in general, with continuing participation of People with Disabilities (PwD). The activation of various municipal committees can facilitate this collaborative approach with the community.

In terms of routines and behaviors, the availability of trees and shades in a city is an answer to aid in accessibility, a point that was also highlighted by the results of previous research activities on site⁵, together with the adequate facilities such as kiosks and toilets, and the complete implementation of the existing legislation. Notably, the group pointed to the poor connectivity to the linear park from its surrounding areas and street network, a local condition that could be improved by implementing best practices from other countries. It emerged that a vision for the future is missing in promoting slow mobility and pedestrian-friendly environments, as well as making the place children-friendly and PwD-friendly. Experiences from the residents revealed that there is a discontinuity in the pedestrian networks around

⁵ Kyprianou, I., Artopoulos, G., Bonomolo, A., Brownlee, T., Cachado, R. Á., Camaioni, C., Đokić, V., D’Onofrio, R., Đukanović, Z., Fasola, S., di Giovanni, C. F., Cocci Grifoni, R., Hadjinicolaou, P., Ilardo, G., Jovanović, P., la Grutta, S., Malizia, V., Marchesani, G. E., Ottone, M. F., Carlucci, S. (2023). Mitigation and adaptation strategies to offset the impacts of climate change on urban health: A European perspective. *Building and Environment*, 110226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BUILDENV.2023.110226>

the park, hence leading to unsafe accessibility mostly for PwD. In terms of mobility inside the park, there are no signs and labels, nor support infrastructure; continuous pavements are interrupted by trees and potholes. In the surroundings, there is a complete lack of greenery, therefore offering no shade for walking to and from the park. Such issues can be vastly improved in terms of accessibility and user experience for the Pedieos River Linear Park if addressed through a collaborative, inclusive, and well-maintained approach to the facility.

Figure 8: Visual Story of Mobility & Accessibility Working Group

For the Visual Story tool, the working group selected the title "Finally Inclusive Planning for All" to be communicated in the news. This initiative will focus on a safe and accessible area for all. Critical among the propositions offered is the assurance that there will be adequate sidewalks in all streets leading to the park from surrounding neighborhoods, together with inclusive planning principles. Making the linear park safe and accessible to serve all residents and tourists.

A few steps in the direction of realizing the goals would be to encourage broader citizen participation, apply public space regulations appropriately, raise awareness about global best practices, and educate stakeholders to make informed decisions.

By 2034, the park will become a daily destination for sustainable mobility, offering the basic services necessary. Further measures would concern constant maintenance, frequent amelioration, and the consolidation of the park as an appealing destination first for the city dwellers and then for the regional ones.

5. Discussion

5.1. Community Feedback

At the end of the workshop, an anonymised questionnaire was distributed and completed by 17 of the 31 participants to collect feedback on their experience of the workshop method, its content and reflections for improvement. The outcomes (Fig.9) suggest that all the participants acknowledge the significance of the community engagement in Strovolos' public space decision-making, with most of them realizing that some practices/behaviors need to change. The expectations of the community for the workshop were mostly fulfilled and its organization and structure received great comments. Participants especially mentioned the opportunity to express their opinions, learn more information about the Pedieos River Linear Park, and listen to the opinions of other community members and experts. Most of the participants were eager to

participate in future activities and excited to discuss in more detail NBS, mobility and accessibility, and the heritage of Strovolos, exploring specific solutions to the challenges identified in this workshop. Due to the various exercises encompassed in this workshop, several participants mentioned the lack of interaction between the working groups, and the insufficient time allowed by the end of the workshop to further discuss the results of each team. Lastly, all responders voted in favor of sharing the results of the workshop with Local Authorities, encouraging the implementation of similar activities in other locations of the region.

Figure 9: Outcomes of the questionnaire distributed after the workshop completion

5.2. Citizen Science

The method used for the implementation of the presented activity is an effort of addressing the complexities and challenges of community engagement, particularly in the context of NBS in urban planning, notably the mistrust of the community toward decision-makers and authorities. Specifically, Cyprus is characterised by limited opportunities of public engagement, mainly consisting of public deliberations (Trutkowski et al., 2017), that drives the community to feel undervalued and overlooked. At the same time, citizen science is an emerging approach, adopted by various fields of research, especially regarding biodiversity, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), and public participation (Kullenberg & Kasperowski, 2016), involving the active engagement of the community in gathering, analyzing, and utilizing data to inform decision-making. Such an approach can empower the community, legitimize their knowledge and experiences, and more importantly involve them in decision-making processes.

Today that digital technologies provide a growing capacity for sharing information, strategic use of digital tools, such as a Public Participation Geographic Information System (PPGIS) platform, can provide opportunities for effective and collaborative exchange of knowledge, data collection, and analysis. A PPGIS platform can become a powerful tool that enables community members to actively contribute their observations, experiences, and concerns in a structured and accessible manner. Then, this can be used as a database of localized knowledge, with real-time and context-specific data can be shared among a network of stakeholders to inform decision-making, thus bridging the gap between top-down decision-making and grassroots input.

The use of digital tools in the context of citizen science and participatory processes offers a robust means of overcoming challenges in community engagement, promoting a transparent knowledge hub for public use that is inclusive and informative. Information and Communication Technology (ICT), digital media and platforms, facilitate collective management and assessment of planning scenarios (Artopoulos et al., 2019). In the context of NBS, such an approach ensures that the solutions are rooted in the community's real needs, leading to a more effective and sustainable outcome, while at the same time strengthening the social fabric and resilience of the community.

5.3. Communication and Data Visualization

In this context, the diversity of stakeholders and community groups with various backgrounds asked for an accessible and equitable way of communicating and visualizing data. The use of digital tools in collaborative processes, such as co-diagnostic and co-creation, could, on the one hand, broaden the capacity to share data, create and test scenarios, and integrate numerous data types of knowledge (audio, images, video, files, etc.), while on the other hand, this would risk the exclusion of social groups with limited digital literacy, thus limiting inclusivity of collaborative efforts and leading to an uneven representation of community needs and perspectives. To address this, the research aims to combine digital tools with physical means to ensure meaningful participation from individuals who may struggle with digital platforms.

To enhance inclusivity and facilitate the use of digital tools, the engagement of younger generations, who often possess rich digital literacy, is essential. Digitally-literate participants can assist with the use of ICT tools, contributing to the enrichment of the proposed PPGIS platform, hence bridging the digital divide and fostering intergenerational collaboration. This way, not only the younger generation grow feelings of ownership over the process, but also the older generation contributes content in processes of sharing historical knowledge and experiences that are acknowledged by youth and can thus be properly documented. The authors envisage that using this integrated collaborative method with diverse community groups can build stronger ties across different social groups and enhance social capital and resilience.

It is rather necessary that the phygital tools developed for such intergenerational collaborative processes are effective and widely communicative, focusing on simplicity and clarity of their design. As those tools address multi-stakeholder audiences, including non-experts and various age groups, their visualization should be straightforward and easily understandable, ensuring their effective operation as "mediators between space and its users" (Artopoulos et al., 2019). User-friendly visualizations ensure broader participation and contribute to reciprocal benefits between space and user, through the process. The authors suggest that an approach such as the one described here can strengthen social capital and ensure equal representation of diverse voices, resulting in more informed and sustainable outcomes, tailored to specific community needs and thus will be integrated in the method developed through the series of workshops to be organized in the context of the research for the establishment of an LL.

6. Conclusion

The activities presented illustrate the importance of democratic and collective decision-making in nature-based solutions (NBS) by exploring methodologies within the Strovolos Pilot case study. The establishment of an LL in Strovolos was initiated with a co-diagnostic workshop, which is elaborated in this research paper. The workshop, designed under the TRANS-lighthouses project, aimed at legitimizing local community knowledge and integrating it with expert advice on the Linear Park of Pedieos River in Strovolos, Cyprus. This workshop contributes to the pathway towards the establishment of a LL with the

engagement of diverse stakeholders, including marginalized groups, for the co-governance of the implemented NBS.

The results of the workshop suggest the critical role of inclusive, meaningful, long-term participation in urban planning and environmental management that goes beyond existing implementations of the concept that are limited to tokenism (Arnstein, 1969, pp. 216–224). Particularly in Cyprus, where governance is highly centralized, and limited local autonomy is the main obstacle to the successful implementation of any participatory project that strives on inclusion. Despite the low participatory culture, the workshop was able to bring together participants from various fields, including local authorities, elected representatives, NGOs, and community members to engage in roundtable discussions and identify the challenges faced by Linear Park, to explore strategies on how to tackle them.

Through the structured conversations and the use of participatory tools like the Visual Story tool, participants were able to share experiences and opinions, develop common understandings, and propose strategies for the future of the place. The discussions were facilitated with a plethora of data, including maps and 360 images, to help participants express their opinions more specifically. It was clear from the workshop results that in decision-making processes, the practice of involving the voices of those who have been marginalized is indispensable. The proposed actions emphasized environmental communication and awareness, while still focusing on regular and efficient care of public spaces to offer accessibility and safety for everyone. The authors argue that this approach adds to the durability and liveliness of the engagement of the local communities in the implementation of inclusive models of NBS governance in the future, thus creating sustainable and more equitable urban environments.

References

- Ansell, C., & Gash, A. (2008). Collaborative Governance in Theory and Practice. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 18(4), 543–571. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jopart/mum032>
- Arnstein, S. R. (1969). A Ladder Of Citizen Participation. *Journal of the American Institute of Planners*, 35(4), 216–224. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944366908977225>
- Artopoulos, G., Arvanitidis, P., & Suomalainen, S. (2019). Using ICT in the Management of Public Open Space as a Commons. In C. Smaniotto Costa, I. Šuklje Erjavec, T. Kenna, M. De Lange, K. Ioannidis, G. Maksymiuk, & M. De Waal (Eds.), *CyberParks The Interface Between People, Places and Technology* (Vol. 11380). Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-13417-4>
- Brennan, M. A., Barnett, R. V., & Lesmeister, M. K. (2007). Enhancing Local Capacity and Youth Involvement in the Community Development Process. *Community Development*, 38(4), 13–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15575330709489816>
- Caitana, B., & Moniz, G. C. (2024). Co-Production Boundaries of Nature-Based Solutions for Urban Regeneration: The Case of a Healthy Corridor. *Cogitatio*, 9(Urban Planning).

<https://doi.org/10.17645/up.7306>

- Costa, C. S., García-Esparza, J. A., & Artopoulos, G. (2024). *Heritage-based storytelling and narratives. The added value of engagement in placemaking and heritage communication.*
- De Vicente Lopez, J., & Matti, C. (2016). *Visual toolbox for system innovation. A resource book for practitioners to map, analyse and facilitate sustainability transitions.* Climate-KIC.
- Fassi, D., De Rosa, A., & Vergani, F. (2021). *Multiple narratives for multiple visions: Engaging citizens in building future scenarios for their city through participatory design and storytelling.* 2, 2942–2954.
- Frantzeskaki, N. (2019). Seven lessons for planning nature-based solutions in cities. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 93, 101–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2018.12.033>
- Giannakis, E., Bruggeman, A., Poulou, D., Zoumides, C., & Eliades, M. (2016). Linear Parks along Urban Rivers: Perceptions of Thermal Comfort and Climate Change Adaptation in Cyprus. *Sustainability*, 8(10), 1023. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8101023>
- Innovation Training. (n.d.). *The World Café Method: Hosting and Facilitating Collaborative Discussion.* <https://www.innovationtraining.org/the-world-cafe-method-hosting-and-facilitating-collaborative-discussion/>
- Iwasaki, Y. (2016). The role of youth engagement in positive youth development and social justice youth development for high-risk, marginalised youth. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, 21(3), 267–278. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673843.2015.1067893>
- Kullenberg, C., & Kasperowski, D. (2016). What Is Citizen Science? – A Scientometric Meta-Analysis. *PLOS ONE*, 11(1), e0147152. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0147152>
- Lekies, K. S., Baker, B., & Baldini, J. (2009). Assessing Participation in Youth Community Action Projects: Opportunities and Barriers. *Community Development*, 40(4), 346–358. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15575330903279648>
- Mahmoud, I., & Morello, E. (2021). Co-creation Pathway for Urban Nature-Based Solutions: Testing a Shared-Governance Approach in Three Cities and Nine Action Labs. *Smart and Sustainable Planning for Cities and Regions*, 259–276. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-57764-3_17
- Nature4Cities. (2018). *Citizen and Stakeholder Engagement strategies and tools for NBS Implementation, deliverable D5.2.* DW. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730468/results>

- Noll, M., Riegler, J., Solerød, M., Gollner, C., & Theierling, S. (2020). *DRIVING URBAN TRANSITIONS: Report on the AGORA Strategic Dialogues*. JPI Urban Europe.
- Norström, A. V., Cvitanovic, C., Löf, M. F., West, S., Wyborn, C., Balvanera, P., Bednarek, A. T., Bennett, E. M., Biggs, R., De Bremond, A., Campbell, B. M., Canadell, J. G., Carpenter, S. R., Folke, C., Fulton, E. A., Gaffney, O., Gelcich, S., Jouffray, J.-B., Leach, M., ... Österblom, H. (2020). Principles for knowledge co-production in sustainability research. *Nature Sustainability*, 3(3), 182–190. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0448-2>
- Nygren, N. V., Jokinen, A., & Nikula, A. (2017). Unlearning in managing wicked biodiversity problems. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 167, 473–482. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2017.06.019>
- PHUSICOS. (2018). *Guiding Framework for Tailored Living Lab Establishment at Concept and Demonstrator Case Study Sites, deliverable D3.1*. TUM. <https://www.phusicos.eu/>
- Strovolos Municipality. (2024). *History*. <https://www.strovolos.org.cy/archiki-selida/o-dimos/gnoriste-to-dimo-strovolou/istoriki-anadromi/>
- Sue, T. (2017). *Nature and Wellbeing in the Digital Age: How to Feel Better Without Logging Off*. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.
- Trutkowski, C., Del Bianco, D., & Loizou, E. (2017). *Training needs analysis of local government in Cyprus*. Council of Europe: Centre of expertise for local government reform.
- Tsang, E. W. K., & Zahra, S. A. (2008). Organizational unlearning. *Human Relations*, 61(10), 1435–1462. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726708095710>
- UNaLab. (2019). *STAKEHOLDERS AND TARGET GROUPS, deliverable D7.1*. Comune di Genova & ERRIN. <https://unalab.eu/en>
- URBiNAT. (2019). *Local Diagnosis Report for each Frontrunner City, deliverable D2.1*. IULM. <https://urbinat.eu/>
- Vetter, T. (2020). Social (un-)learning and the legitimization of marginalized knowledge: How a new community of practice tries to 'kick the grain habit' in ruminant livestock farming. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 79, 11–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2020.08.036>
- Wenger, E., McDermott, R. A., & Snyder, W. (2004). *Cultivating Communities of Practice: A Guide to*

Managing Knowledge. HARVARD BUSINESS SCHOOL PRESS.

World Bank. (2021). *A Catalogue of Nature-Based Solutions for Urban Resilience*. World Bank.

<https://doi.org/10.1596/36507>

PREPRINT

Table of Figures

[Figure 1: Conceptual Diagram of Co-diagnostic approach followed for the co-production of knowledge](#)

[Figure 2: A model of collaborative governance \(Ansell & Gash, 2008\)](#)

[Figure 3: Cyprus' governance model, illustrated by the authors, based on \(Trutkowski et al., 2017\)](#)

[Figure 4: Co-diagnostic workshop methodology to trigger unlearning for NBS implementation \(illustrated by the authors\)](#)

[Figure 5: Fill-in templates for each working group, with pre-defined topics for discussion \(created by the authors\)](#)

[Figure 6: Visual Story of Biodiversity & Environment Working Group](#)

[Figure 7: Visual Story of Public Space & Activities Working group](#)

[Figure 8: Visual Story of Mobility & Accessibility Working Group](#)

[Figure 9: Outcomes of the questionnaire distributed after the workshop completion](#)

PREPRINT

Appendix 1: Results from the discussion within the working groups

Discussion Results			
	Biodiversity & Environment	Public Space & Activities	Mobility & Accessibility
Participatory Culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > The main actors involved in decision-making about the Pedeios River Linear Park are the Water Development Department and the Environment Department. > Informed decision-making should consider the engagement of scientists and biologists, as well as local initiatives and community members. > There is pressure applied to the Municipality from local community groups and citizens, but not a formalized participatory process. > Regarding the reduction of the cat population in the park, a collaboration among the community, scientists, and the Municipality should be formed. > There is a conflict between the scientists who argue for the negative impacts of a large population of cats in the river's ecosystem and the residents who take care of the cats and feel they are responsible for them and shouldn't abandon them. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Various agencies are involved in decision-making, including government, municipality, and the police. > Participatory practices should be in place to ensure holistic and successful decision-making. > Initiatives for collaborative endeavors should be encouraged, to include diverse stakeholders > The decision-making process is very bureaucratic, and cannot address issues effectively. > More volunteerism should be encouraged with diverse groups acting toward changing our culture/behavior. > Especially for the Pedeios River Linear Part, there are jurisdictional limitations, as diverse agencies are responsible for different tasks. > There is a lack of accountability from the side of the government and the municipality. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Community voice is not heard in decision-making, especially for their neighborhood, and city > Political decisions are forced on the community without their involvement. > Decision-making should be a collaborative process, including governmental agencies, scientists, and researchers. > PwD should be invited to express their needs and priorities to be taken into account in planning. > The more social groups participating, the more valuable insights and ideas. > Participation should be an ongoing process, and not just public deliberations after the project is decided. > The various municipal committees should be activated and work with the community.
Routines & Behaviors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > There is a strong human impact on the ecosystem especially with invasive species (cats, crayfish, etc.). > Human-centric needs for water resulted in the interruption of water flow in the river with a dam, water diversion, and pollution from urban and industrial wastes. > Anthropocentric interventions result in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > There is a lack of mentality for park use in Cyprus. Urban nature is not much appreciated. > The linear park is essential for physical activities, jogging and cycling. > Relationships with nature and a pleasant landscape can positively impact mental health. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Trees and shade facilitate accessibility. > Lack of amenities, such as kiosks, WC, etc. to encourage mobility. The existing regulations are not applied. > Lack of connectivity between the adjacent neighborhoods and the linear park.

	<p>pollution and consequent disruption of the ecosystem as well as stagnant waters and flooding.</p> <p>> Lack of environmental education and awareness for all age groups, to learn about the local species and ecosystems.</p>	<p>> More actions should take place to promote nature-based solutions, caring for nature, and raising awareness of the environment.</p> <p>> There is a need for a participatory tool so that citizens can constantly raise concerns or report issues.</p>	<p>> Parks are improving mental health through contact with nature, socialization, and exercise.</p> <p>> Lack of promotion and learning from international best practices.</p> <p>> The park should be more welcoming to kids and PwD.</p> <p>> Lack of vision and political will to promote slow mobility and pedestrians.</p>
Experiences	<p>> The plastic containers for cat's food are polluting the environment and the ecosystem.</p> <p>> The food placed for the cats, also attracts foxes that can be dangerous for the park users.</p> <p>> Taking care of stray cats does not solve the problem. A campaign for sterilizing them should take place.</p> <p>> Polluted water is affecting not only the ecosystem but also the people's health.</p> <p>> Caring for the cats also supports other species. For example, the water placed for the cats is also used by several birds in the area.</p>	<p>> It is very important that the linear park offers a free public green space in the urbanized environment.</p> <p>> People are mainly using it to exercise and for leisure. It is also a popular spot for migrants.</p> <p>> There is difficult access from the city because of the vegetation.</p> <p>> The flooding is making the park inaccessible.</p> <p>> The lack of lightning creates a feeling of unsafety, especially during the night.</p> <p>> Low maintenance makes the park unsafe and hard to access by PwD.</p> <p>> There is great potential to promote sustainable and renewable energy through the park, as well as the circular economy.</p> <p>> There is great potential to host various activities in the park for youth, and schools, and add amenities, such as playgrounds, kiosks, and WC.</p>	<p>> Diverse experiences of the residents create diverse opinions on different topics.</p> <p>> The pedestrian networks around Pedieos River Linear Park are not continuous, resulting in unsafe accessibility to the park (occasional lack of sidewalks) and difficulties for PwD.</p> <p>> Lack of signs, labels, and infrastructure to support and facilitate PwD. The paths are interrupted by trees, potholes, etc. interrupting the mobility within the park.</p> <p>> The surroundings of the park lack greenery, and therefore there is no shade to walk to and from the park.</p> <p>> Flooding is a result of bad mobility infrastructure (the road follows the morphology of the river's bank instead of a bridge).</p> <p>> Behavioral change can only be achieved if there is compliance with the laws and law enforcement from the authorities.</p>

Appendix 2: Visual Story tool results for each working group

Visual Story Tool Results			
	Biodiversity & Environment	Public Space & Activities	Mobility & Accessibility
News Title	<i>THE STRAY CATS OF THE LINEAR PARK HAVE BEEN REDUCED TO ¼ THROUGH CONSTANT STERILIZATION.</i>	<i>A SAFE LINEAR PARK FOR ALL, ALL DAY LONG</i>	<i>FINALLY INCLUSIVE PLANNING FOR ALL</i>
Propositions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Management of the growing population of cats in the linear park. > Engagement of diverse stakeholders in matters related to the park. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Cultivate a collaborative spirit among community, government, and NGOs > Clean and maintain the river bank from waste and overgrown vegetation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > All streets that lead to the park from the surrounding neighborhoods have adequate sidewalks. > Inclusive planning based on principles and methods. The linear park concerns all the residents and tourists of the area. > The linear park is finally safe for everyone.
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Realize that the growing population of cats is not healthy for the river's ecosystem > Define what means to be an animal lover > Address health issues related to stray cats > Address political and bureaucratic barriers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Fear of attack from sketchy people and stray dogs. > Availability of WC, clean drinkable water, and sufficient lightning. > Maintenance of the park to be safe. Remove fallen trees and fix the pathways from rocks and potholes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Exclusivity of specific social groups. > Lack of political will for change and vision by all stakeholders. > Ineffective applications of regulations. > Lack of awareness regarding the historical importance of the river and its role in the development of the urban landscape.
Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Municipality > Relevant Governmental Agencies > Veterinarians > Animal Welfare Organizations > Scientists > Community (Residents and Park Users) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Municipality > Town & Planning Department > Fire Department > Water Development Department > Community > NGOs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Municipality > Relevant Governmental Agencies > Youth > Citizens > Community groups, associations, and collectives

Book of Proceedings

[Learnings/Unlearnings: Environmental Pedagogies, Play, Policies, and Spatial Design](#) conference,

Färgfabriken, September 5-7, 2024

<p>Steps</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Mass communication campaign. > Review best practices of other countries. > Raise awareness and change the mentality of common/sharing spaces. > Full engagement of the Municipality and other relevant actors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Inform relevant specialists, scientists, and the wider public. > Improve the sense of safety along the linear park. > Learn from best practices around the globe. > Encourage events organization in the linear park. > Improve mobility and accessibility. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Wider participation of citizens, relevant agents, and media for communicating activities to the public, also through social media and digital platforms. > Application of correct specifications and legislation for public space. > Raising awareness of best practices from around the globe. > Adequate education of stakeholders involved for informed decision-making.
<p>Future Achievements</p>	<p>Year 2030:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Transparent communication of the process by all stakeholders. > Implemented strategy. > Respect over common spaces and their maintenance and protection. > Applied regulations and law enforcement. 	<p>Year 2025:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Emergency spots are introduced every couple of km along the linear park. > Lights are installed throughout the linear park and operate consistently when they are needed. > People do not walk their dogs without a leash, since this is enforced by law. > A Pedieos linear park 'safety team' is on standby 24/7 and a dedicated hotline is set up for people to receive immediate help if and when needed. 	<p>Year 2023:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > The linear park is finally connected to the surrounding neighborhoods. > The linear park connects the different municipalities and across the divide (buffer zone) to the north (occupied areas) > The linear park is used daily for sustainable mobility as an integral part of the mobility network. > The linear park serves as a destination for the users since it offers the necessary amenities and facilities.
<p>Next Steps</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Total reduction of the cat population in the Pedieos River Linear Park. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Defibrillators can be found easily throughout the linear park. > The health team is on standby 24/7. > Linear park is maintained consistently. No trees or potholes can cause danger to the users of the park. > A team regularly patrolling the linear park is formed and put into action. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> .> Constant maintenance of the park. > Frequent improvements when necessary. > The park becomes a pole of attraction for local and regional residents.

Appendix 3: Prescript Stories for initiating working group discussion

Biodiversity & Environment:

1. We are Vanya and Malin, a couple from Russia who recently moved to Cyprus. We live in Strovolos and for the last few months we have been using the pedestrian path of the park daily to exercise. We really like it and enjoy it, but last April we had an unexpected revelation. After a strong sudden rainstorm, the river level rose, and in certain places stagnant water was created, which remained like this for about a week, until it dried up. During this week the place was filled with mosquitoes, flies and other flying things, and the smell was unbearable.
2. My name is Gianna and I am a proud animal lover. In my house I host eleven kittens and countless birds, while I feed the kittens at point X of the linear park every day. This is something I enjoy and it fills me up, despite the backlash. Every afternoon I'll take the car and go to the linear park to feed the kittens and leave. I don't know who feeds them in the morning, but someone has taken over that shift judging by the leftovers I find when I arrive. Sometimes, in the winter, I will also take any old furniture that I have, along with a couple of old blankets, so that the poor cats don't get cold.
3. We are Angela and Nefeli, two students at the University of Cyprus, friends since childhood, who still live with their parents in Strovolos. Since our first year at university we have joined the Environmental Club and have taken part in countless campaigns to clean up beaches, green spaces, picnic areas, forests and rivers. As local Strovolos' residents, the campaign in the linear park of Pedieos river was both the most rewarding and the most frustrating. What we saw was unexpected. The riverbed was filled with construction site waste, clothing, footwear, suitcases, bags, food and drink packaging, and anything else you can imagine. And through it all we saw frogs, reptiles, birds, bees, and when night fell, even if you don't believe us, we saw a fox.
4. Spotty (the stray dog) calls the Pedieos Linear Park his home. He loves the open spaces where he can run freely and the occasional scraps of food left behind by picnickers. On Sundays, Spotty enjoys following families around, hoping for a friendly pat or a treat. However, his peaceful life was disrupted when people started blocking his usual paths with parked cars and bicycles. Despite these obstacles, Spotty finds solace in the kindness of regular park-goers who recognize him and ensure he is fed and cared for.
5. Chirpy (the bird) loves the tall trees of Pedieos Linear Park, where she has built her nest. She enjoys singing to the morning sun and watching the people pass by below. The park provides plenty of insects and seeds for her to eat. However, Chirpy often finds plastic and other trash tangled in her nesting materials. Despite this, she continues to build her nest, finding joy in the daily interactions with other birds and the occasional kind human who leaves birdseed near her tree. Her life became very stressful lately as she had to fly away from her nest many times to avoid being caught by feral cats. She had a few calm encounters with Whiskers the Cat in the past but recently she found no peace in the trees of Pedieos near the Strovolos Town Hall and had to rebuild her nest away towards Lakatamia.

Activities & Public Space

1. I am Ganesh, from India, and I have been in Cyprus for the last 2.5 years for work. Together with four other compatriots we use the outdoor gym located at point X of the linear park to exercise. We really like it and enjoy it, since it's something we do together. We often have a bet on who can do the most push-ups and pull-ups, and the loser has to cook the next day. Also, most of the time we are the only ones using it, and we can work out comfortably. So I can work out and enjoy food effortlessly!

2. I am Yannis, I am a student from Cyprus and I am 10 years old. Every day after school my friends and I gather on the linear park with the bikes, and we race. Once I fell off my bike and scraped my knee badly. Unfortunately there was no source of water near me, and so, being ashamed to go home, I was left with a soiled knee until the evening. Not only did it hurt when my mom was cleaning it for me, I was also grounded.
3. I'm Lin, a cleaning lady and I'm from Vietnam. On Sundays, when I am on outside chores, I cross the linear park on my electric bike to go from my house to the house I will clean. At midday, even though it is unbearably hot, riding through the linear park offers some comfort. In the afternoons, when the pedestrian and bicycle traffic is increased, my riding becomes difficult. Pedestrians often stay in the middle of the road even though I honk at them, and resent it when I insist. Sometimes they shout at me, but I don't always understand what they say.
4. I'm Niki and I'm 28 years old. I am a young employee in an accounting office, and I like sports and fitness. I play tennis every week, and I've been training for a marathon for the last 3 months, after work, at the linear park. I usually run with a friend for company, but 3 weeks ago, when he was abroad, I continued my training alone. That's when I feared for my life. It was about 9:30 in the evening, and I was on my way back when I felt someone following me. A man came out of the trees on the side of the road and started running after me. From the looks of it he didn't seem to be in the park for exercise. I started running faster and so did he. Due to my good physical condition, I was able to keep my distance and luckily I reached my car quickly. He followed me and tried to get in, I caught up and locked the doors. I was shaking all over, but I managed to start the car and drive away. I went to the police to file a complaint, I also reported it to the Municipality. So far I haven't received any response, maybe I'll try again.

Mobility & Accessibility

1. I am Kostas and I live with my wife and children in the Strovolos area, next to the linear park. This has its pros and cons. First, we have easy access to the pedestrian path, where we go for a walk with the children every Sunday afternoon. Also my wife uses it daily for jogging. On the other hand, passers-by often pass through our garden, at the point where it joins the pedestrian path, talking loudly and walking over the children's toys that remain in the garden.
2. I'm Irini and I work in a real estate office. I cross the linear park every day by car to go to work. I am disappointed with the Municipality, the road project managers, other drivers, pedestrians and cyclists. At rush hours, on the way to work in the morning and on the way home in the afternoon, it becomes pandemonium. Horns everywhere, exhaust fumes from cars, shouting, swearing... Bicycles and electric scooters are constantly cutting the road. With each car that moves a little further, traffic stops again for pedestrians and cyclists to cross. And cars enter from the side, cutting me off.
3. I am Achilles and I am 80 years old. Last year I had an accident that disabled my knee, and since then I have limited mobility. My activities are very few: I take care of the flowers in the garden and every afternoon I do my exercise by walking on the sidewalk in front of my house. I'm lucky, because the sidewalk, where I'm walking, doesn't have any cars parked. Unfortunately, all my other travel has been curtailed. The linear park is 300 meters from the yard of my house. I tried to do my exercise there: go to the sidewalk, rest on the bench and come back, but it was impossible. Unfortunately, due to the fact that this particular point is an entrance to the cycle path and a pedestrian path, in the afternoons it is blocked by parked cars and there is no room for my wheelchair to pass.

Appendix 4: Questionnaire for the completion of the co-diagnostic workshop on 19 July 2024

	Not at all	Very Little	Fairly	Mostly	Fully
1. The expectations I had for the workshop were fulfilled. These expectations were: _____ _____ _____ _____	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2. The workshop's procedure gave me the opportunity to express my opinion.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3. I believe that my opinion will contribute to the development of the project.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4. It was interesting to listen to the information shared by the experts.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5. After the workshop, I realized that some practices/behaviors need to change.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6. I believe that it is significant for the community to collaborate for Strovolo's public space.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7. The workshop's content was interesting. Next time, I would like to discuss about: _____ _____ _____	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8. I am content with the organization and activities of the workshop. Next time, I would like: _____ _____ _____	<input type="checkbox"/>				
9. The workshop and the topic of the project are interesting and I would like to participate again.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
10. It is important for the outcomes of the workshop to be shared with the authorities.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

11. I wish more similar workshops would be organized in other areas of the Nicosia region.

PREPRINT